

LINGUISTIC APPROACH TO IMPLICATION

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Annotation

This article focuses on the term implication and its functions in current world linguistics. It also discusses its role in the structure of the text.

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The term “implication” came from the science of logic, and in this regard, O.I. Prosyannikova says that “it means that linguists are not just interested in logical constructions, but also turn to a special aspect of the semantics of language - inferential relations” [1,36], in addition to these thoughts, she explains implication with the following formula: “The linguistic concept of implication, unlike logic, implies the non-representation of one of the two components of a logical operation - the result. Linguistic implication derives the following relations from a logical operation, but the content of the components in this chain is significantly different and is expressed by a different formula, which includes three components:

$A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$.

Here B is a specific statement based on A (implied by the speaker's meaning or assumption), and B itself simultaneously expresses a certain conclusion of the recipient - C is the implication itself. is based on the speaker's practical experience, general knowledge about the world. By extracting additional information from the message, the participant in the dialogue uses the capabilities of language and knowledge that has a pragmatic nature. In addition, extralinguistic means, namely gesture, mimicry, artistic details, also serve as the basis for implication”[1,35]. The presence of explicit (factual) and implicit information in the text indicates the existence of two types of text structure, in which case implicit information plays a key role in revealing the content of the text.[1,35] It should also be noted that in oral speech, explicitness prevails over implicitness. Traditionally, implicitness is considered within the framework of philosophical and linguistic approaches. According to philosophical approaches, ambiguity is explained as an indirectly presented judgment, conclusion. In the linguistic approach, the discrepancy between the plane of form and content and

the conclusions arising from this are studied. As for the use of implicitness in a work of art, here we are talking about its special role in revealing the author's artistic intention. Often, ambiguity is a special technique used by the author to express and create a more expressive work of art works as. In this case, hidden information becomes a separate load, deepening the semantic structure of the text and giving the work a unique aesthetic load. In some literature, this phenomenon is called implicit meaning. A number of linguists believe that implicit meaning is a meaning that arises from the text, that the speaker, using implicit meaning, is able to change the semantic and even emotional-psychological content of the text without expanding its volume, that implicit meaning secretly complements the content of the text and partially or completely changes the content semantically.

In our opinion, implicitness is not the exact meaning of the message, but a method chosen by the writer or speaker to increase expressiveness.

According to I.A. Sternin, usually in texts of any type, information can be expressed in several ways:

- 1) in an explicit verbal form, an expression or a chain of expressions is openly stated, there is a clear logical predicate of the sentence.
- 2) in an implicit verbal form, information is expressed verbally, but the information expected from it is not immediately understood, logicity usually refers to the possessive group.
- 3) in the form of presupposition, although direct information about some aspects of the event in the text is not given, both the speaker and the listener can guess this content.

The intended meaning is expressed in the text in completely different linguistic units, but the recipient can “extract” the necessary semantic meanings from the text [2,20]. In this case, the writer does not state his thoughts explicitly, but rather refers to other means. At the same time, he must be able to evoke certain associations in the addressee so that the implicit thought is understood.

M.V. Nikitin in his works calls implication “a type of conceptual connection”. A.V. Bondarko dwells on the problem of implicitness in detail. He emphasizes that its content components “arise from the relationship and influence of explicitly expressed semantic elements, not directly expressed by specific linguistic means”, [3, 175].

Indeed, hidden content structures and speech acts arise due to the representations existing in the minds of people. That is, initially the explicit meaning is embodied before our eyes, and through it other hidden, mysterious

meanings can manifest themselves differently in the thinking of each speaker and perceiver. The set or generalization of such different representations is formed in the language as a single semantic paradigm, generalized within the framework of a single common content.

According to the researcher A.V. Starkova, who is engaged in structural grammar, “implicitness can only be realized through sentences, it cannot be expressed by morphemes, words or word combinations”[3]. Supporting these views of the scientist, we can say that in order to form structurally implicit meanings, a certain situation, context, is certainly required. This, in turn, is achieved with the help of sentences. However, in the process of analyzing artistic details in our study, we became convinced that a single detail, appropriately selected and included by the writer to reveal the character of the image in psychological prose texts, can form implicit meanings in itself. We will dwell on this in the following chapters.

S.S. Karsevsky, in his research, describes implicitness as a specific, separate phenomenon: “Implicitness is an asymmetric dualism of a linguistic sign, the essence of which is that in this case the sign and the essence do not completely encompass each other”[4]. According to the above ideas, in addition to the meaning expressed by the sign itself, there is also an implied meaning. This is a hidden meaning, which is manifested in harmony with the context. Continuing S.S. Karsevsky’s analysis of implicitness in structural linguistics, E.I. Shendels defines it as follows: “Implicitness is a general objective property of the language system, which is revealed in speech in the form of an implication in relation to the subject”[6,175]. It should be noted that in linguistics, the term “implication” is also used together with the term “implicitness”. There are different views on the use of these terms in linguistics. In O.S. Akhmanova’s “Dictionary of Linguistic Terms”, the term “implication” is considered as “implied” (“podrazumevanie”)[10, 607]. Implied, hinted at indicates the essence of implication. Yakubova N. writes in her study: “implication is a specific form of implicitness, which means that hidden meanings are assumed, accepted, and concluded differently by different recipients. In general, although there is no sharp difference between these two terms, in terms of content and structure, implicitness (hidden meaning) is taken as a broader concept than implication. That is why linguists try to supplement the term implication in their studies.”

Based on the works of the Russian linguist O.I. Moskalskaya, it can be said that the phenomenon of implication is based on “situational connections or the relationship between the whole and the part”[11, 183]. Because this

phenomenon is based on the author-text-reader chain, when the implication phenomenon is reflected in the text as a result of the author's communicative intention, it is perceived by the reader, the reader, relying on his knowledge, thinking, and worldview. V.A. Kukhareenko, a contemporary of the author of this concept, emphasizes in his studies that "the basis of implication is the perception of additional semantic or emotional content that is not directly reflected in the syntagmatically realized meanings of text units,"[12,327]. Based on this, it can be said that the linguistic units that make up the implicit structure partially lose their semantic meaning and serve to form the character of the image or the idea of the work. E.N. Starikova defines implicitness as "the lack of exact expression of structural elements that convey deep meaning in a sentence"[7,142], while I.V. Arnold, a researcher who pays special attention to the concept of textual implication, defines it as: "An implied, additional meaning based on the syntagmatic connections of antecedent elements"[7].

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